

TEACHER'S PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AND PROFESSIONAL CULTURE ENHANCEMENT FACTORS

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Abstract. *Today's demand requires the educator to improve his professional skills, knowledge, ingenuity, creativity, as well as personal qualities. This article discusses the challenges of developing a future educator's pedagogical skills and professional culture.*

Keywords: *teacher, educator, competence, pedagogical skills, professional competence, functional responsibilities of the teacher, pedagogical ability, pedagogical technique, pedagogical qualimetry, pedagogical attitude.*

Improving pedagogical skills and developing professional culture of educators is of great importance in ensuring the implementation of reforms in the preschool education system today. In particular, the fact that educators learn more about their profession and work more on themselves guarantees that they will successfully work in post-school educational organizations in the future. Achieving pedagogical skills is achieved with certain personal qualities of the pedagogue. Pedagogical skills represent the development of pedagogical activities, acquisition of pedagogical techniques, as well as the personality of the pedagogue, his experience, civil and professional status.

The scientific approaches of recent years have made it possible to draw the following conclusion in relation to this situation: pedagogical skill is understood as a bright manifestation of individuality in professional activity. The dynamism of the implemented changes, new strategic directions in the development of the economy, politics, socio-cultural sphere objectively advance the problem of quality training of professional and pedagogical personnel. Updating and changing the goals and tasks of education, forming new educational structures, new content of education, preparation for professional activity, pedagogical self-determination, self-organization and self-requires new technologies for training educators with self-management skills. The professional-pedagogical education system plays an important role in fulfilling this task.

When it comes to preschool education, even more demands and responsibilities are required from the educator and pedagogue. Because preschool education is considered the first stage of education, 70% of the child's initial knowledge is acquired in preschool education. The role of the educator is very important for the solid and wide acquisition of this knowledge.

Humanity is the most important basis for the personality of a modern pedagogue. A teacher is a person with a very high level of culture. He should know a lot, he should be aware of the achievements and news in the field of science he is studying. In order to teach students daily activities, he should regularly study, learn, fill and deepen his knowledge.

Pedagogical skill is not an innate or hereditary trait, but a product of research and creative work. This multifaceted pedagogical activity is based on creative work. If we look at the professional skills program of the pedagogue in practice, then the first place is its integral quality - skill. Despite the fact that there are so many definitions of pedagogical skill, some aspects of skill are definitely expressed in them.

LITERATURE REVIEW. Mastery is a high and rising art of training and teaching. A pedagogue is a master of his work, an in-depth knowledge of his subject, well-acquainted with relevant fields of science and art, well-versed in general and youth psychology in practice, well-versed in the methodology of teaching and upbringing, and highly cultured specialist. The role of lectures is as important as the role of seminars in improving the skills of future professionals.

The famous pedagogue Abdulla Avloni also gives a special place in his works to the expression of views on the personality of the teacher and his activities. According to Alloma, if parents play a special role in the healthy growth of a child, the teacher's role in his intellectual development is incomparable. In particular, he emphasized that the formation of children's mental abilities is a "sacred task that rests on the attention of teachers and is entrusted to their conscience" and says that "the strength, ornamentation, breadth of thought depends on the education of the teacher."

In his time, Jan Amos Comenius greatly appreciated the role of the teacher in the development of the child's worldview, and emphasized that teaching is "a very proud profession that is higher than any other profession on earth." According to the author, it is necessary for a pedagogue to have a deep understanding of his duties and to be able to fully appreciate his value. Describing the image of a teacher, Ya.A. Komensky emphasizes the expediency of the following qualities in his person: conscientious, hardworking, consistent, moral, loves his work, treats students like their fathers, and instills knowledge in them. awe-inspiring, reader-following, and religious faith.

K. D. Ushinsky highly evaluates the morale and professional activity of teachers and puts forward the opinion that it is appropriate to constantly improve their professional skills. The system that confirms the social importance of this idea is the first to justify the system of training teachers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. Preschool life is a small pedagogical process and is very diverse. There are situations that do not correspond to the pedagogical theory. This requires extensive knowledge, thorough practical training, high pedagogical skills and creativity from the pedagogue.

The professional skill of an educator is the sum of certain personal (love of children, kindness, benevolence, etc.) and professional (knowledge, sense of responsibility, creativity, erudition, etc.) qualities, and he is the optimal way of raising children in his pedagogical-psychological and methodological preparation. It is manifested in the search for them. Therefore, along with professional skills, knowledge, intelligence, and creativity of the teacher, it is necessary to improve personal qualities as well. Mahir must first of all have ideological training. What we mean by this is that national values, customs, and traditions should be shared and delivered to the minds of young people, and they should be able to raise respect for the rich heritage created by our ancestors. For this, first of all, the coach needs to have a deep understanding of the essence of national values, to be able to respect them, to have a clear understanding of the laws of social life, to understand the content of national-moral values, ideology, it is important to educate students to respect the spirit of ancestors and descendants, the foundations of a scientific worldview. becomes important.

In the pedagogical field: love of children and interest in working with them, love of pedagogical work, mental pedagogical intelligence and observation, pedagogical tenderness,

pedagogical imagination, organizational skills, honesty, sincerity, demandingness, determination and goal-seeking, self-control, professional competence.

In the field of knowledge: broad scientific level, spiritual need and interest, intellectual interest, ability to feel new. Activities enrich a person with the experience of analyzing and summarizing the events encountered. Pedagogical qualification is the ability to acquire acquired knowledge and skills in a certain type of activity and perform it well. This is the true scientificity of understanding and knowledge, the skill of an authoritative leader who is able to overcome difficulties in education, the ability to feel the heart of children, the skillful approach to the personality of a child whose inner world is delicate and weak, wisdom and creative courage, scientific analysis, imagination and the capacity for fantasy is embodied.

RESULTS. It should be noted that the profession of pedagogy is a complex and responsible profession. The honor and complexity of this profession is determined by the fact that it is always in communication with a person who is the only owner of consciousness. A conscious and living creature is constantly developing mentally, spiritually and physically. Therefore, in order to influence him, he should regularly study subjects such as psychology and educational theory, and constantly work on his professional skills. It provides pedagogical, psychological and methodical training of teachers.

Pedagogical skills are content in the pedagogical process. Pedagogical process provides professional and personal training, prepares the future specialist for work and life, prepares specialists who are responsible for the state, society, nation and the future generation. Therefore, a pedagogue should have personal and professional qualities.

Based on the above-mentioned definition of pedagogical skill, as well as the characteristics of the educator's profession and socio-economic, political and cultural requirements for pedagogues, the theory of pedagogy states that pedagogical skill should consist of the following main components (components).

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION. Pedagogical culture-educational duty, responsibility, dignity, conscience, moral belief means demandingness, justice, perfection, truthfulness, correctness of the pedagogue. Pedagogical tact (tact) in the system of pedagogical skills is characterized as the measure, norm and limit of the pedagogical purposeful, useful, valuable actions of the pedagogue. The listed components of pedagogical skills enrich the professional characteristics of a pedagogue and lead him to mastery, and help the teacher to develop pedagogical skills. However, relying solely on them to become a master of your profession may not yield the expected results. For this, it is necessary to regularly think pedagogically, think pedagogically, and do pedagogic work. This means that it is necessary to analyze the pedagogical events and situations of one's activity, to try to understand their connections, to independently analyze the daily results and to get used to comparing new educational ideas with the previous ones. It is necessary to find the main pedagogical and psychological problems and to think about finding the most convenient ways to solve them.

Humanism is a concept that expresses concern for the creation of conditions for the manifestation of all the principles of humanity about human dignity, freedom, happiness and equal rights. Taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of pedagogues, the correct use of their opportunities; correct attitude towards predictable situations, rational assessment of others' success, fairness in material and moral incentives.

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